

June 30, 2019

Organic Fertilizers Use By Small Scale Vegetable Farmers in Ejusu-Juaben Municipality in Ashanti Region of Ghana

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Martin Bosompem ⁽²⁾ Frank A. Acheampong

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension-School of Agriculture University of Cape Coast, Cape Coast, Ghana.

Abstract

The study examined the key factors that influence the use of organic fertilizers among vegetable farmers. Fifty (50) vegetable farmers from four communities in Ejusu-Juaben Municipality in the Ashanti Region of Ghana who had ever consciously used organic fertilizers on their farms were interviewed to understand the key factors that influence their use of organic fertilizer in vegetable farming. Even though the majority of the key informants who used organic fertilizers were of the view that it is available, affordable and improved the productivity and quality of vegetables produced significantly, only a few (12%) continued to apply it. The key reasons for continuous application by the farmers were that organic fertilizers last longer in the soil as compare to inorganic fertilizers, an increase in yield and quality of their produce. The main reasons given for discontinuance of the use of organic fertilizer include 1. unhygienic nature of the fertilizer, hence its association with pest and disease after the application, 2. less yield compared to inorganic fertilizers 3. Bulkiness during transportation and 4. Difficulty in its application. To improve the use of organic fertilizers in vegetable production, efforts by government and agro-processors should be directed at the processing and packaging of organic fertilizers for portability, hygiene, and ease of use. They should also create the necessary (including environmental and health) awareness on the importance of organic produce, and the policy support for certification and pricing of organic produce.

Keywords: Organic fertilizer use; small scale farmers, Vegetable farmers, Ghana.

INTRODUCTION

The growing concern of climate change and concerns of consumers about safer foods have led to a general consensus among many agricultural development practitioners in the world that agricultural goals should not only emphasis increase production (for an ever increasing population) but also prevent soil erosion, reduce pesticide and fertilizers contamination, protect biodiversity, preserve natural resources and other relevant climatic indicators, and improve well-being (Hamideh, Kurosh & Abdol-Azim, 2011). An environmental impact assessment done in Europe with respect to organic farming concluded that organic farming performs better than conventional farming in relation to key environmental indicator categories including the ecosystem, soil, climate and air, ground and surface water, farm input and output, animal health and welfare and quality of food produced (Stolze, Piorr, Häring & Dabbert, 2000). This impact assessment showed that organic farming can mitigate some of the effects of climate change in Ghana and Africa as well as provide safer food compared to conventional farming.

A major component of organic farming is the use of organic fertilizers comprising mostly of manures and composts. Before the introduction of mineral fertilizers about 150 years ago, it is reported that manure and composts were practically the only sources of nutrients to crops (Aldrich, 1972). In Organic fertilization, the nutrients are derived from the remains or by-product of plants or animals such as poultry manure, compost, cow dung, crop residues, and green manure. Thus, its decomposition and release of the nutrients depend on activities of soil microbes and soil conditions such as moisture and temperature.

The use of agrochemicals is widespread among farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa. There is little evidence

June 30, 2019

of knowledge and adoption of improved soil fertility management and crop protection practices of a non chemical nature amongst farmers in sub-Saharan Africa. The management of soil organic matter is an essential component of the overall management of tropical soils because of the role it plays in soil fertility. This is particularly important in an agricultural system such as Ghana where there is little use of fertilizers if it is to improve agricultural productivity. A survey by Harris, Lloyd, Hofny-Collins, Barret and Browne, (1998) on 132 community development groups in 24 Sub-Saharan countries including Ghana and Kenya revealed that organic farming can encounter wide range of constraints in relation to finance, degree of familiarity with inorganic fertilizers versus organic fertilizer management techniques, land size, and ownership, the degree of intensification of the farming systems and unavailability of alternatives to inorganic inputs.

It is estimated that approximately 25% of the world's crops today are produced with inorganic fertilizers and as such, the demand for inorganic fertilizers has been doubling every 10 years (Pidwirny, 2002). Soil organic matter, its composition and the process of humification, plays a central role in soil fertility. Organic fertilizers are unquestionably the most useful aid in maintaining soil fertility and should be used whenever it is practicable and economical. According to Webster Wilson (1980), organic fertilizers have given better results than an equivalent amount of nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus in inorganic fertilizers. On the contrary, inorganic fertilizers are expensive and generally unaffordable by farmers. Furthermore, continuous use of inorganic fertilizers such as sulfate of ammonia, commonly used as a side dressing, ultimately makes the soil acidic which poses danger to optimal crop growth and yield (Antwi, Tsimese and Kusi, 1999). Over application of inorganic fertilizers renders the fruits of the crops logged, and unwholesome due to the accumulation of chemicals in the form of water which increases their perishability, and a threat to human health. On the contrary, organic fertilizers have been found to improve bacterial and fungal activities increase in the soil, increase soil water – holding capacity and improve the physical structure which allows more air to get to the plant roots.

Researchers, agricultural practitioners, and others are advocating for methods of farming that can mitigate climate change outcomes and protect the environment of which organic farming, as well as the use of organic fertilizer, is crucial. Farmers in Ghana seem unwilling to use organic fertilizers such as poultry manure, green manure, cow dung in vegetable production systems even though they are readily available. Furthermore, agriculturists and scientists and others are advocating for a shift from chemical farming to more sustainable and ecologically sound farming often described as organic farming or ecological farming. Anecdotal reports and interaction with some vegetable farmers at the study area revealed that the use of organic fertilizers in vegetable production was low although they knew of the benefits of organic fertilizers. Therefore, why the low adoption of organic fertilizers among vegetable farmers in spite of their knowledge of its benefits for sustainable crop production, and what factors can influence its use among vegetable farmers in the area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A case study was used to examine vegetable farmers who have consciously used organic fertilizers from four (4) communities in the Ejisu-Juaben Municipality including Boankra, Kubease, Baworo and Tikrom areas in the Ashanti Region of Ghana. Ejisu-Juaben Municipal is one of the 27 administrative Districts in the Ashanti Region of Ghana (There are 10 regions in Ghana). The Municipal covers an area of 637.2 km². It lies within Latitude 1° 15' N and 1 ° 45' N and Longitude 6° 15'W and 7° 00'W. About 94.1 % of the farmers are into crop production. The favorable climatic conditions and the geophysical characteristics of the area support intensive crop farming. purposes. The major food crops cultivated **are** maize, plantain, cassava, cocoyam, and **vegetables**. Rainfall averaged between 1200mm and 1500mm with a double maxima rainfall starting from March to July and from September to latter part of November. Temperatures range between 20°C in August and 32°C in March. The relative humidity is fairly moderate but quite high during rainy seasons and early mornings. The fair distribution of temperature and rainfall patterns helps in the cultivation of many food and

June 30, 2019

cash crops throughout the Municipality making it possible for minor season farming hence making the District a food- sufficiency case in Ghana. The Municipal lies within the semi-deciduous forest zone, which does not differ much in appearance from the Rain Forest. Most of the trees shed their leaves during the dry season, but not at the same time for all the trees of the same species. (<http://www.ghanadistricts.com/districts,2012>)

The area was chosen because a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) has created awareness in the district for the use of organic fertilizer and other organic farming practices in the area (Network for Ecofarming in Africa, 2002).

A combination of purposive sampling, snowballing and convenient (accidental) sampling was used to select fifty (50) key informants who had used organic fertilizers on their vegetable farms. An interview schedule with both closed and open ended questions were used for the data collection. Descriptive statistics including frequencies and percentages were used in the analysis of the data. Charts were also used. These statistics and charts were only for the purpose of organizing the responses of the informants for better understanding. The intention is not to generalize the findings to other populations of vegetable farmers in Ghana and elsewhere. But there is much that can be learned by other vegetable farmers, researchers and policymakers to inform theory, practice, and policy regarding organic farming in Ghana.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics of the selected Vegetable farmers.

The results show that majority of the farmers (about 58%) who participated in the study had between 1-10 years of experience as vegetable farmers. They were predominantly males (90%) and about a half (54%) were in their productive age (21-40 years), as vegetable farmers (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Vegetable Farmers

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	45	90
	Female	5	10
Educational Level	No formal education	11	22.0
	Basic level	32	64.0
	Sec./Tec./Voc.	6	12.0
	Tertiary	1	2.0
Age (Years)	21-30	7	14
	31- 40	22	44.0
	41 - 50	13	26.0
	51 – 60	3	6.0
Experience (Years)	1-10	30	57.7
	11-20	15	28.8
	21-30	7	13.5

n = 50

Seventy-eight percent of the respondents had had some form of formal education with the majority (64%) of them at the basic level. Low level of education could affect the rate of adoption of an innovation since education makes a farmer more receptive to advise from an extension agent or able to understand more the technical recommendations (Gamble & Gamble, 2002).

Type of Vegetables Grown and Fertilizer Used

The results of the study show that most of the vegetable farmers were into Tomato (48%) and pepper (22%) production (Table 2). Other important vegetables grown by the farmers were garden eggs, cabbage,

June 30, 2019

cucumber, and carrot. Most of the farmers indicated that organic fertilizers are best for vegetables especially Cabbage and Carrot. The tomato farmers, however, indicated that they use the inorganic fertilizers more than organic fertilizers because the organic fertilizers take a longer time to decompose before planting.

Table 2: Type of Vegetable grown by respondents

Vegetable	Frequency	Percentage
Tomato	24	48.0
Pepper	11	22.0
Garden eggs	5	10.0
Cabbage	4	8.0
Other Vegetables	6	12
Total	50	100.0

n = 50

As presented in Table 3, majority of the vegetable farmers (approximately 88%) currently use inorganic fertilizers to maintain or improve upon the fertility of their soil even though they were aware of the importance and benefits of organic fertilizers. Harris, *et al* (1998) observed that the percentage of farmers using inorganic fertilizers was significantly higher in peri-urban than in rural areas. Most of the farmers said even though they had used organic fertilizers before they stopped using it because it is difficult to apply, takes a longer period to decompose, unhygienic and not useful when it does not rain.

Table 3: Type of Fertilizer Used by Respondents

Type of fertilizer used currently	Frequency	Percentage
Inorganic fertilizers only	28	56
Organic fertilizers only	6	12
Combination of organic and inorganic fertilizers	16	32
Total	50	100.0
Type of organic fertilizer used	Frequency	Percentage
Farm Yard Manure	38	76
Compost	10	20
Green Manure	2	4
Total	50	100.0

The results show that Farm Yard Manure (FYM) and compost were the most important organic fertilizers used by the farmers. Most of the farmers (76%) used FYM because they claimed it is readily available, though it takes longer time to decompose to release nutrients (Table 3). The FYM was mostly from poultry droppings and cow dung. Only a few famers (20%) had used compost even though it has been identified as the most appropriate organic fertilizer for vegetable production especially if it does not contain any animal matter.

Cost, availability, and willingness to use organic fertilizers

Regarding the cost, the farmers were asked to indicate the major cost they incur in the use of organic fertilizers. The cost of transportation and purchasing of the organic fertilizers were the two key cost elements.

June 30, 2019

In terms of the importance of the cost elements, the majority of informants (70%) pointed to transportation (Table 4). This is not surprising because organic fertilizers by the nature (mainly FYM) as used in Ghana are bulky and untidy and more likely to attract higher transportation cost by transporters who would agree to provide such services. Harris, *et al* (1998) had commented on similar cost and difficulties of transporting organic fertilizers as major constraints in the use of organic fertilizers in sub Saharan Africa. Interestingly, about half (52%) of the farmers did not purchase the manure (it was free) and therefore transportation cost was the only cost they incurred in getting the manure to their farms.

Table 4: Main Cost elements of respondents in using organic fertilizers

Major Cost Elements	Frequency	Percentage
Transportation only	26	52
Purchasing only	15	30
Both transportation and purchasing	9	18
Total	50	100

n = 50

Having limited funds to purchase inorganic fertilizers was rated as an important reason frequently cited by farmers in Ghana, Malawi, Kenya, Niger and Uganda for adopting alternative soil management techniques such as the use of organic fertilizers (Harris, *et al.* 1998). Also, as reported by USDA (1980), organic fertilizers generally have lower input cost than inorganic fertilizers. Consequently, some farmers, especially those on small scale farms with cash flow problems, can shift to the use of organic fertilizers to reduce their cash flow needs (Lampkin and Padel,1994).

Availability and Effect of Organic fertilizer on Yield

Figure 1 shows farmers' perceptions of the availability of organic fertilizers in the area of study. As the general belief, the study confirms that organic fertilizers are available in Ghana for crop production, especially vegetables. Approximately 86 % of the farmers indicated that organic fertilizers are available in the area they operate.

Figure. 1: Farmers perceptions on the availability of Organic Fertilizers in study Area

June 30, 2019

n = 50

From the figure 2, the majority (82%) of the farmers had an increase in outputs when they used organic fertilizers on their vegetable farms. Dennison (1975) asserted that organic fertilizers gave higher yields than the equivalent amount of NPK fertilizers in long-term continuously cropped soil. Doughty (1970) had long ago supported the idea that organic fertilizers gave higher yields than inorganic fertilizers.

Figure 2: Farmers’ perception of the effect of organic fertilizers on yield
Farmers Willingness to use Organic Fertilizers if Available

The respondents were asked if they would like to use organic fertilizers as against inorganic fertilizers if both are readily available. Majority of the farmers (60%) said they were not willing to use organic fertilizers as against inorganic fertilizers if both are readily available (Figure 3). None of the respondents identified any environmental reasons for using or not using organic fertilizers implying that farmers’ knowledge level of the benefit of using organic fertilizers was limited to only economic benefits not environmental. Harris, *et al.* (1998) found that organic agriculture is unlikely to be adopted without one or more of the following: active government policy supporting organic agriculture; producer demand to farm organically for philosophical, religious, scientific, intuitive, environmental or health reasons; or economic incentive in the form of subsidy or premium price for organic produce.

Figure 3: Farmers willingness to use organic fertilizers as against inorganic fertilizers if both are readily

available.

Reasons why vegetable farmers continue to use organic fertilizers

Table 5 presents the reasons why vegetable uses organic fertilizers as against inorganic fertilizers.

Table 5: Reasons why vegetable farmers continue to Use Organic Fertilizer

Reasons	Response (% score)	Rank
Organic fertilizers increase the quality of vegetables.	40	1
Organic fertilizers last long in the soil	30	2
Organic fertilizers increase yield.	20	3
Want to try how organic fertilizers work.	10	4
Total	100	-

N=50

The main reasons why vegetable farmers stopped using organic fertilizers and resorted to the use of inorganic fertilizers are presented in ranking order in Table 6. The major reasons given were that organic fertilizer is unhygienic compared to the inorganic counterpart (26.7%), the yield is relatively lower in organic fertilizer (16.6%) and it bulkiness to transport and apply on the field 15.6). Other reasons given were lack of Technical know-how on the use of different kind of organic fertilizers, lack of knowledge on how it works and the fact that organic fertilizer works slower compared to the use of inorganic fertilizers.

Table 6: Reasons for discontinuing the use of Organic fertilizer by Vegetable Farmer

Reason	Percentage (%)	Rank
Organic fertilizer is unhygienic compared to inorganic	26.7	1
Inorganic fertilizers yield Higher than the organic fertilizers	16.7	2
Bulky to transport and Apply (use) Organic fertilizer	15.7	3
Do not know how to use the different kinds of organic fertilizers	14.3	4
Do not know how the organic fertilizers work	13.3	5
Organic fertilizers work slower compared to inorganic	13.3	5
Total	100	

N=50

Waithaka, Thornton, Shepherd, and Ndiwa, (2007) and Shepherd, Ohlsson, Okalebo, Ndufa and David (1995) have also reported that organic fertilizers especially Manure and compost are bulky to carry, hence require much labor to carry and spread on the fields. Agyarko, & Adomako (2007) reported the bulkiness and transportation difficulties associated with organic manure were as the major limiting factors affecting the use of manures among farmers in Sissala district, Shama-Ahanta East and Birim South districts of Ghana. Also, Place, Barrett, Freeman, Ramisch, and Vanlauwe (2003) and Palm, Myers, and Nandwa (1997) have reported that manure releases nutrients to the soil slowly and helps soils to build organic matter with long-term benefits. Therefore, even though respondent farmers regarded the slow release of nutrient of organic fertilizers as a reason for discontinuing its use, it is actually an advantage and this confirms their acknowledgment of the low level of knowledge on how to use organic fertilizer and how it works in the soil.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

June 30, 2019

Conclusions

Majority of the vegetable farmers in the study area were males, in their productive ages and with considerable years of experience in vegetable farming but low level of education.

Majority of the vegetable farmers in the study area grow tomatoes and pepper and currently using inorganic fertilizers to maintain or improve the fertility of their soils. Those who used organic fertilizer used mostly Farm Yard Manure. The most important cost incurred by farmers when using organic fertilizers was transportation cost although there are few who purchased the organic fertilizers. Majority of the vegetable farmers perceived organic fertilizer as readily available in the area but were not willing to use them. The main reasons are given for not willing to use organic fertilizers include 1. unhygienic nature of the fertilizer 2. bulkiness during transportation, a 3. longer period of decomposition, 4. difficulty in its application, and 5. its association with pests and diseases after application. Farmers who were willing to use organic fertilizer were of the opinion that organic fertilizers last longer in the soil as compare to inorganic fertilizers, and increase the yield and quality of their produce.

Even though farmers were aware of some of the benefit of using organic fertilizers to increase yields and income, they were not aware of the environmental impact of the use of organic fertilizers on their farms.

Recommendations

The following recommendations can inform policy and practice for improving organic fertilizer use among vegetable farmers in Ghana.

The government of Ghana should develop an organic farming policy which includes the use of organic fertilizers. The policy must address standards of producing organic produce an economic incentive in the form of subsidy to farmers who enter into organic farming. This will call for awareness creation among both farmers and consumers on the environmental and health benefits of organic agriculture.

To improve the use of organic fertilizers in Ghana, organic fertilizers should be processed, bagged and sold as done with chemical fertilizers. The government of Ghana and the private sector, including agro-processors and entrepreneurs should collaborate to process and package organic fertilizers for portability, hygiene, and ease of use in the country.

References:

- i. Agyarko, K., & Adomako, W. J. (2007). *Survey of the use of organic manure among vegetable farmers in selected districts in Ghana. Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 9(4), 1-15.
- II. Aldrich, P.M. (1972): *West African Agriculture (3rd edn.)*. Oxford University Press: Oxford.
- iii. Antwi, E.L.K. Tsimese Appiah, B. K. (1999). *Small-scale composting for literature number 2*.
- iv. Dennison, E.B. (1975): *The Value of Farmyard manure in maintaining fertilizer in Northern Nigeria. Dennison, Empire J. Exp. Agric.* 29 (116): 330-336.
- v. Doughty, L.R. (1970): *The Value of Fertilizers in African Agriculture. Field Experiments in Africa*.
- vi. Gamble, T. K & Gamble.M. (2002). *Communication works. (7th ed.)*. Mc Graw- Hill (Irwin. Inc.: New York. pg 82- 107)
- vii. Hamideh, M.; Kurosh, R., & Abdol-Azim, A. (2011) *Iranian agricultural professionals' knowledge on organic farming: African Journal of Agricultural Research* 6(2), pp. 907-915: Available online at <http://www.academicjournals.org/AJAR>
- viii. Harris, P.J.C., Lloyd, H.D., Hofny-Collins, A.H., Barret, A.R. & Browne, A.W. (1998): *Organic Agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa: Farmer Demand and Potential for Development. The Henry Doubleday Research Association (Garden Organic): Coventry, UK*.
- ix. <http://www.ghanadistricts.com/districts> (2012)

June 30, 2019

- x. Lampkin, N.H & S. Padel. (1994): *The Economics of organic Farming. An international perspective.* Network for Ecofarming in Africa (2002). *Workshop Documentation on International Follow-up Workshop Strategies of Ecofarming Promotion in Africa October 14 - 25, 2002, Jinja, Republic of Uganda*
- xi. Place, F. Barrett, C.B, Freeman, H.A., Ramisch, J.J, and Vanlauwe, B. (2003) *Prospects for integrated soil fertility management using organic and inorganic inputs: evidence from smallholder African agricultural systems.* *Food Policy* 28:365–378
- xii. Palm, C.A., Myers, R.J.K., Nandwa, S.M. (1997) *Combined use of organic and inorganic nutrient sources for soil fertility maintenance and replenishment.* In: Buresh RJ, Sanchez PA, Calhoun F (eds) *Replenishing soil fertility in Africa.* Soil Science Society of America, Madison, Wisconsin.
- xiii. Shepherd, K.D, Ohlsson, E., Okalebo, J.R., Ndufa, J.K, David, S. (1995) *A static model of nutrient flow on mixed farms in the highlands of western Kenya to explore the possible impact of improved management.* In: JM Powell, Fernandez-Rivera S, Williams TO, Renard C (eds) *Livestock and sustainable nutrient cycling in mixed farming systems in sub-Saharan Africa. Proceedings of an international conference, 22–26 November 1993, held at the International Livestock Centre for Africa, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.* ILCA, Addis Ababa, pp 523–538.
- xiv. Stolze, M, Piorr, A, Häring, A., & Dabbert, S (2000) *The Environmental Impacts of Organic Farming in Europe* *Organic Farming in Europe: Economics and Policy* 6 (Stephan Dabbert, Nicolas Lampkin, Johannes Michelsen, Hiltrud Nieberg, Raffaele Zanolli, University of Hohenheim, Department of Farm Economics: Germany
- xv. USDA (1980): *Report and Recommendations on Organic Farming,* US Government printing office, Washington D.C.
- xvi. Webster, C.C. & Wilson, P. N. (1980): *Agriculture in the Tropics (2nd ED)* Longman Group UK Ltd.
- xvii. Waithaka, M.M, Thornton P.K., Shepherd, K.D. & Ndiwa, N.N. (2007) *Factors affecting the use of fertilizers and manure by smallholders: the case of Vihiga, western Kenya.* *Nutr Cycl Agroecosyst* 78:211–224.